

BEHIND THE FRIENDLY FACADE: THE EMOTIONAL BURDEN OF BEING A “STRONG FRIEND” AMONG SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the lived experiences of Senior High School students identified as “strong friends,” or peer-group emotional anchors, to examine the psychological and social costs of sustained emotional labor and suppressed vulnerability. Using a qualitative interpretive phenomenological design, the study involved 15 Grade 12 students from Sucat Senior High School in Muntinlupa City selected through referral sampling. Data were gathered through a researcher-made semi-structured interview guide in private one-on-one interviews, with ethical safeguards for informed consent, confidentiality, and emotional well-being. Audio-recorded narratives were transcribed verbatim and analyzed through thematic analysis, including data familiarization, initial coding, clustering of subthemes, theme refinement, and thematic mapping. Findings revealed that strong friends experienced emotional dissonance, compassion fatigue, paradoxical isolation, pressure to meet others’ expectations, and a persistent support gap shaped by emotional masking and fear of becoming a burden. Participants commonly coped through self-silencing, distraction, surface acting, and self-reliance, while expressing unmet needs for validation, reciprocity, safe spaces, and supportive boundaries. The study contributes to the growing literature on adolescent peer support by foregrounding the hidden emotional burden carried by student caregivers and by offering evidence that schools must recognize and respond to the often invisible vulnerability of those who are habitually expected to remain strong.

Keywords: *strong friends, emotional labor, peer support, adolescent vulnerability, thematic analysis*

INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is a developmental period marked by intensified emotional, social, and academic demands, making it a particularly sensitive stage for mental health risk and psychosocial adjustment. The World Health Organization reported that one in seven adolescents aged 10–19 years experiences a mental disorder, with depression and anxiety among the leading causes of illness and disability in this age group (World Health Organization, 2025). At the same time, peer relationships become increasingly central to adolescent development because they shape identity, belonging, emotional regulation, and everyday coping. Supportive peer relationships are therefore not peripheral to adolescent well-being; they are among the social conditions that can either buffer stress or compound it, depending on how they are experienced and sustained (Mitic et al., 2021; Scardera et al., 2020).

A substantial body of literature has shown that perceived social support is associated with better psychological functioning among children and adolescents. Meta-analytic evidence indicates that stronger perceived social support is linked to lower depressive symptoms, while longitudinal evidence suggests that adolescents who perceive greater support are less likely to report later depression, anxiety, suicidal ideation, and suicide attempts (Rueger et al., 2016; Scardera et al., 2020). These patterns align with the stress-buffering perspective, which explains how supportive relationships protect individuals from the harmful effects of stress exposure (Cohen & Wills, 1985). In schools, this protective role is especially salient because adolescents often encounter academic pressure, performance expectations, and social uncertainty simultaneously. Within such environments, peer support can serve as an accessible and emotionally meaningful resource for coping and adjustment.

However, the literature on peer support is far more developed in explaining the benefits of receiving support than the emotional costs of consistently providing it. This imbalance is crucial in understanding the socially recognized yet conceptually underexplored figure often described by students as the “strong friend”, the peer who is expected to listen, absorb distress, remain composed, and stabilize others while concealing personal struggles. From the standpoint of emotion regulation, adolescents actively manage how emotions are experienced and expressed in social contexts (Gross, 1998). When that regulation becomes habitual performance for the sake of others, it begins to resemble emotional labor, or the management of feeling and emotional display according to social expectations (Hochschild, 2012). Research on emotional labor has repeatedly shown that surface acting such as projecting calmness, strength, or positivity without corresponding internal states, is associated with emotional exhaustion and strain (Grandey, 2003; Grandey & Gabriel, 2015). Although this literature emerged largely from occupational settings, its core insight is strikingly relevant to adolescent peer dynamics: repeatedly performing strength can become psychologically costly.

The hidden burden carried by the “strong friend” may be intensified by barriers to help-seeking that are already common among young people. A systematic review of youth mental health help-seeking found that stigma, embarrassment, poor symptom recognition, and preference for self-reliance are among the most common barriers preventing adolescents and young adults from seeking support (Gulliver et al., 2010). In the Filipino context, these concerns are compounded by cultural and structural factors. Martinez et al. (2020) found that Filipinos generally show reluctance toward formal help-seeking and often prefer close family and friends as sources of support, while self-reliance, shame, stigma, and “loss of face” remain important obstacles. Earlier work on Filipino youth likewise showed that young people often turn to peers as part of their coping ecology, suggesting that support is frequently negotiated within relational rather than formal structures (Guanzon-Lapena et al., 2009). Together, these patterns create a quiet paradox: the adolescents most relied upon by their peers may themselves be the least likely to disclose distress or seek assistance.

This issue is timely in the Philippine senior high school context, where student mental health concerns have become more visible while supportive school responses remain uneven. Philippine studies have documented the importance of social support to student well-being and the persistence of anxiety, distress, and other mental health risks among senior high school learners. Otero et al. (2024), for instance, found a positive association between social support and psychological well-being among senior high school students in Davao del Norte, while Serrano et al. (2023) emphasized the need to strengthen social support in school mental health programs for senior high school students in Metro Manila. Delanoche and Mamba (2024) likewise underscored the relevance of school-based mental health interventions after identifying significant anxiety and distress among senior high school students. Yet these studies, valuable as they are, focus mainly on general well-being, mental health risks, or support availability; they do not directly examine the emotional consequences experienced by students who repeatedly occupy the helper role within peer networks.

Literature suggests a meaningful gap. Existing research explains why peer support matters, why young people often prefer informal support, and why help-seeking can be difficult; however, it offers limited insight into the lived experience of adolescents who are persistently expected to be emotionally available, resilient, and dependable for others. This gap appears especially relevant in Philippine school settings, where relational closeness can make peer support both protective and burdensome. Addressing this blind spot, the present study explores the lived experiences of Senior High School students who identify with or are recognized in the role of the “strong friend,” with particular attention to the psychological and social impacts of sustained emotional labor, the coping mechanisms they use, the barriers that inhibit their own help-seeking, and the support they believe would genuinely reduce emotional exhaustion. By foregrounding the voices of student peer supporters, the study contributes a more nuanced understanding of adolescent support systems and offers an empirical basis for more responsive school-based psychosocial interventions.

Research Questions

1. What psychological and social impacts do 'strong friends' experience as they consistently maintain a façade of resilience while suppressing their own emotional needs?
2. What coping mechanisms do 'strong friends' use to manage their emotional burden, and what barriers prevent them from seeking or receiving support from peers or adults?
3. How do 'strong friends' describe their unmet emotional needs and the types of support they believe would genuinely help reduce emotional exhaustion?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative interpretive phenomenological design to examine the lived experiences of Senior High School students who occupy the role of the "strong friend" within their peer groups. This design was appropriate because the inquiry focused on understanding how participants make sense of sustained emotional responsibility, suppressed vulnerability, and the hidden burden of being relied upon by others. The study was conducted in Sucat Senior High School, a public senior high school in Muntinlupa City, Philippines.

The participants were 15 Grade 12 students identified by their peers as emotional anchors or the individuals most often approached for advice, comfort, and emotional support. Referral sampling (snowball sampling) was used because students who fit the strong-friend role are not readily identifiable through random selection and often conceal their own distress. Initial referrals were obtained from student leaders or class officers, after which identified participants referred other students who met the inclusion criteria. Participants were selected based on the following characteristics: emotional reliability, prioritization of others' needs, emotional masking, self-reliance during personal difficulties, strong empathic capacity, and a sense of hyper-responsibility for remaining emotionally available to peers.

Data were gathered using a researcher-made semi-structured interview guide composed of open-ended questions designed to elicit detailed accounts of participants' emotional experiences, coping responses, barriers to help-seeking, and perceived support needs. The instrument was subjected to expert review by qualified evaluators knowledgeable in adolescent psychosocial concerns, including a school counselor and a psychologist, to establish content validity, clarity, and ethical appropriateness. It also underwent pilot testing to improve question wording and participant comprehensibility. The instrument was structured to generate rich narrative data. Measures to strengthen trustworthiness included member checking and peer debriefing..

Data collection proceeded in three stages: preparation, referral, and interview. After securing the necessary permission and preparing informed consent materials, the researchers identified qualified participants through referral sampling. Individual one-on-

one interviews were then conducted in quiet and private areas within the school to ensure psychological safety and confidentiality. Each interview lasted approximately 30 to 45 minutes and was audio-recorded with participant consent. Participants were given adequate time to describe their lived experiences freely, while the interview guide was used to maintain focus on the objectives of the study.

The data were analyzed using thematic analysis. Audio-recorded interviews were transcribed verbatim and reviewed repeatedly during the data familiarization stage. Significant statements, recurring expressions, and emotionally salient experiences were identified through initial coding. Related codes were then clustered into subthemes and broader themes that captured shared patterns across participants' narratives. These themes were reviewed, refined, and organized to ensure analytic coherence and fidelity to participants' accounts. A thematic map was subsequently developed to illustrate the relationships among the emergent themes and to support interpretation of the lived experience of being a strong friend.

The study was delimited to Grade 12 students in one public senior high school in Muntinlupa City who were identified as strong friends within their peer networks. It focused specifically on their psychological and social experiences, coping mechanisms, barriers to disclosure, and perceived support needs. Because the study used a small, non-probability sample from a single site, the findings are not intended for statistical generalization. Rather, they offer an in-depth and context-bound understanding of a specific adolescent experience that may inform school-based psychosocial support initiatives.

RESULTS

Table 1

The psychological and social impacts of being a "strong friend"

Theme	Description	Illustrative participant expression
Emotional dissonance	Participants experienced a mismatch between their true feelings and the emotions they displayed to others.	"Laging nagtatago sa likod ng ngiti"; "Ayaw nilang makita sila na mahina..."
Compassion fatigue and emotional depletion	Constantly receiving and carrying others' emotional burdens left participants drained and internally exhausted.	"Drains or empties the person"; "Bawal sila mapagod"; "Laging nagtatago sa likod ng ngiti"
Paradoxical isolation	Despite being surrounded by peers and valued as dependable companions, participants felt	"Drains or empties the person"; "Ayaw nilang

	personally unseen and emotionally alone.	makita sila na mahina kasi sila yung inaasahan”
High-expectation pressure	Participants felt pressured to maintain a resilient image because others relied on them as the stable one.	“Ayaw nilang makita sila na mahina kasi sila yung inaasahan”; “Bawal sila mapagod”

Table 2
Coping mechanisms and barriers to help-seeking

Theme	Description	Illustrative participant expression
Surface acting	Participants coped by smiling, appearing calm, and concealing emotional strain to preserve group stability.	“Laging nagtatago sa likod ng ngiti”; “Ayaw nilang makita sila na mahina...”
Distraction and emotional avoidance	Academic work and busyness were used to suppress distress rather than process it directly.	“Laging nagtatago sa likod ng ngiti”
Self-reliance and self-silencing	Participants often believed they had to endure their struggles alone because asking for help contradicted their role.	“Bawal sila mapagod”; “Ayaw nilang makita sila na mahina kasi sila yung inaasahan”
Fear of being a burden	Participants avoided disclosure to keep from adding emotional weight to others.	“Ayaw nilang maging extra weight or add sa problems ng friends nila”
Helper identity as barrier	Being known as the dependable one made receiving care feel inconsistent with their social role.	“Bawal sila mapagod”; “Ayaw nilang makita sila na mahina kasi sila yung inaasahan”
Perceived imbalance in support	Participants recognized that they were often expected to give support without receiving the same in return.	“Para sa akin kasi... parang unfair din. Dapat parehas kayo may sinasabi”; “Unfair”

Table 3
Unmet emotional needs and desired support

Theme	Description	Illustrative participant expression
Need for validation	Participants wanted someone who would listen without dismissing their vulnerability through reminders that they were “strong.”	“Makikinig lang talaga at hindi sasabihan na ‘O, kaya mo yan, strong ka eh”
Need for reciprocity	Participants desired balanced relationships in which emotional sharing was mutual rather than one-sided.	“Para sa akin kasi... parang unfair din. Dapat parehas kayo may sinasabi”
Need for safe spaces	Participants wanted environments where they could express vulnerability without fear of judgment or role disruption.	“Pwede kang maging vulnerable nang walang takot”
Need for emotionally responsive support	Participants preferred support that is concrete, proactive, and emotionally literate rather than reactive or superficial.	“Maganda yung may mga seminars or workshops para matutunan kung paano i-handle yung emotions”
Need to be seen beyond the ‘strong’ role	Participants wanted others to recognize that being dependable does not mean being emotionally unaffected.	“Makikinig lang talaga...”; “Pwede kang maging vulnerable nang walang takot”; “Ayaw nilang makita sila na mahina kasi sila yung inaasahan”

DISCUSSION

Discussion of Table 1: Psychological and social impacts of being a “strong friend”

Table 1 shows that the experience of being a “strong friend” is characterized by emotional dissonance, compassion fatigue and emotional depletion, paradoxical isolation, and high-expectation pressure. These themes suggest that participants were not simply resilient peers; rather, they were adolescents managing a persistent gap between what they genuinely felt and what they believed they were expected to display. This finding aligns with Gross’s (1998) view of emotion regulation as the management of emotional experience and expression in response to situational demands. However, in the present study, such regulation appeared less adaptive than protective, as participants

used it to conceal distress and preserve their image as dependable companions. In this sense, the findings also support the emotional labor perspective of Grandey (2003) and Grandey and Gabriel (2015), particularly the idea that repeatedly displaying socially expected emotions despite inner strain can lead to emotional exhaustion. Although emotional labor has often been discussed in workplace settings, the present findings indicate that a similar process may operate in adolescent peer relationships, where the expectation to remain “strong” becomes a socially enforced role.

The themes of compassion fatigue and paradoxical isolation further extend the literature on peer support. Previous studies have consistently shown that social support is associated with lower depressive symptoms, anxiety, and suicide-related outcomes among adolescents and young adults (Rueger et al., 2016; Scardera et al., 2020), and that supportive peer relationships are developmentally beneficial (Mitic et al., 2021). The present findings do not contradict this literature; instead, they refine it by showing that support may become burdensome when it is chronically one-sided. Participants were socially valued because others relied on them, yet they also felt unseen and emotionally alone. This pattern suggests that the protective function of social support may weaken when students are consistently positioned as providers of care rather than legitimate recipients of it. The findings therefore add an important nuance to the literature: peer support is most protective when it is mutual, rather than emotionally concentrated in one student who is expected to absorb others’ distress.

From a practical standpoint, the findings in Table 1 imply that schools should avoid assuming that dependable, emotionally composed students are necessarily coping well. Students who are frequently perceived as “the strong one” may be carrying hidden emotional strain that remains unnoticed precisely because they appear functional. In light of evidence that social support is strongly related to adolescent well-being in both international and Philippine contexts (Otero et al., 2024; Serrano et al., 2023), schools may need to broaden their psychosocial lens to include not only visibly distressed students but also those whose distress is masked by competence, composure, and social reliability.

Discussion of Table 2: Coping mechanisms and barriers to help-seeking

Table 2 indicates that participants relied on surface acting, distraction and emotional avoidance, and self-reliance and self-silencing to manage emotional burden, while fear of being a burden, helper identity, and perceived imbalance in support prevented them from seeking or receiving help. These findings suggest that the coping strategies of strong friends are not necessarily healthy resolutions of distress, but often short-term ways of maintaining relational stability. Surface acting, in particular, mirrors the emotional labor framework discussed by Grandey (2003), where individuals display calmness and control despite experiencing internal strain. In the present study, smiling, appearing okay, and suppressing vulnerability functioned as strategies for protecting peers and preserving one’s social role, but they also prolonged emotional concealment. Thus, what may look like resilience from the outside may actually represent exhaustion under disciplined emotional performance.

The barriers to help-seeking identified in Table 2 are also strongly consistent with prior literature. Gulliver et al. (2010) found that adolescents and young adults commonly avoid seeking help because of stigma, embarrassment, and preference for self-reliance. Similarly, Martinez et al. (2020) reported that Filipino help-seeking is often constrained by shame, concern about burdening others, and a tendency toward self-reliance. The present findings align with these studies, but also extend them by showing that help-seeking barriers among strong friends are not merely individual hesitations; they are tied to a social identity. Participants did not remain silent only because they were uncomfortable seeking help, but because asking for support seemed incompatible with being the person others depend on. This deepens the interpretation of self-reliance: for strong friends, silence is not just personal preference but part of the role they feel obligated to maintain.

The theme of perceived imbalance in support is especially significant because it reveals that participants were not rejecting peer relationships altogether; rather, they were questioning the fairness of relationships in which they were expected to give support continuously without receiving comparable care. This finding extends Mitic et al. (2021) by suggesting that supportive peer relationships are not defined only by emotional availability, but also by reciprocity. When care flows in one direction for too long, supportive relationships may cease to be protective and instead become emotionally extractive. In this sense, the results suggest that the problem is not peer support itself, but the unequal distribution of emotional labor within friendships.

The practical implication of Table 2 is that school-based mental health efforts should not focus solely on encouraging students to “speak up.” That message is too thin for students whose silence is rooted in identity, empathy, and role expectations. Schools may need to create structures that normalize help-seeking even among high-functioning peer supporters, such as guided check-ins, emotionally literate peer programs, and classroom or guidance interventions that explicitly challenge the belief that dependable students must always carry distress alone.

Discussion of Table 3: Unmet emotional needs and desired support

Table 3 shows that participants expressed a need for validation, reciprocity, safe spaces, emotionally responsive support, and recognition beyond the “strong” role. These themes suggest that what strong friends need is not more praise for being resilient, but more permission to be vulnerable without being redirected back into the identity of the capable helper. The need for validation is particularly telling. Participants wanted someone who would listen without dismissing their distress with statements such as “you are strong anyway.” This implies that reassurance can become invalidating when it prevents emotional disclosure from being fully acknowledged. In this respect, the findings reinforce the broader social support literature, which emphasizes that support is protective not simply because relationships exist, but because support is perceived as available, responsive, and appropriate to one’s needs (Cohen & Wills, 1985; Scardera et al., 2020).

The themes of reciprocity and safe spaces further clarify that connectedness alone is not enough. Participants were embedded in peer networks, yet still felt emotionally unsupported when their relationships did not allow role reversal, balanced sharing, or fear-free vulnerability. This finding is consistent with evidence that social support contributes to adolescent psychological well-being (Rueger et al., 2016; Otero et al., 2024), but it also sharpens that evidence by identifying a condition for its effectiveness: support must be mutual and psychologically safe. Without these conditions, adolescents may remain socially surrounded but emotionally unattended. The present study therefore extends the literature by showing that the quality of support for strong friends depends not only on whether peers are present, but on whether those peers can also recognize and receive the vulnerability of the person who usually helps.

Participants' preference for emotionally responsive support, including seminars, workshops, and opportunities to learn how to manage emotions, has clear implications for school practice. This is especially relevant given ongoing concerns about adolescent mental health globally and in Philippine schools (World Health Organization, 2025; Serrano et al., 2023; Delanoche & Mamba, 2024). The findings suggest that effective school responses should include structured and non-stigmatizing spaces where emotionally burdened students can speak without judgment, receive validation, and develop healthy coping strategies. Such interventions should not be limited to students who overtly present with crisis or behavioral difficulty; they should also include those who appear composed but may be silently carrying the emotional demands of others.

The final theme, the need to be seen beyond the "strong" role, may be understood as the central conceptual contribution of Table 3 and of the study as a whole. It captures the paradox running across all three tables: students may be admired for their dependability while simultaneously being denied care because that dependability obscures their own need for support. This finding adds to the literature by suggesting that resilience in adolescent peer contexts may sometimes function as a social performance rather than a stable internal strength. For schools, the implication is straightforward but important: the students who most often care for others should not automatically be treated as the least in need of care. They may, in fact, require some of the most intentional recognition, reciprocity, and psychosocial support.

Conclusions

This study concludes that "strong friends" experience significant psychological and social costs as they maintain a façade of resilience while suppressing their own emotional needs. In response to the first research question, the findings show that these students are not simply emotionally strong or well-adjusted; rather, they experience emotional dissonance, compassion fatigue, emotional depletion, paradoxical isolation, and pressure to sustain a dependable image. Their outward composure often conceals inner distress, suggesting that the role of the strong friend is sustained through emotional masking rather than genuine emotional ease. Although they are valued within their peer groups, they may simultaneously feel unseen, burdened, and alone. Thus, the study

reveals that the social position of being relied upon can come at the cost of emotional visibility and personal well-being.

In response to the second research question, the study concludes that “strong friends” manage their emotional burden primarily through surface acting, distraction, emotional avoidance, self-reliance, and self-silencing. These coping mechanisms allow them to maintain their role as the stable and dependable peer, but they do not necessarily relieve emotional strain. Instead, they often prolong concealment and reinforce internal exhaustion. At the same time, several barriers prevent them from seeking or receiving support, including fear of being a burden, discomfort with role reversal, helper identity, and perceived imbalance in support within friendships. These findings indicate that silence among strong friends is not merely a matter of personal reluctance, but is closely tied to social expectations and the internalized belief that they must remain emotionally available for others while handling their own struggles alone.

In response to the third research question, the study concludes that “strong friends” have clear but often unmet emotional needs. They need validation, reciprocity, safe spaces for vulnerability, emotionally responsive support, and recognition beyond their identity as the strong one. Rather than being praised simply for their resilience, they want opportunities to be heard without judgment, to receive care without feeling that they are violating their social role, and to participate in relationships where emotional support is mutual. They also identify the value of structured and emotionally literate support systems, such as safe conversations, guided peer support, and school-based interventions that normalize vulnerability and help-seeking.

The study concludes that the “strong friend” role is shaped by hidden emotional labor, unequal support dynamics, and unrecognized vulnerability. While these students are often perceived as sources of strength, they may in fact be among those most in need of intentional psychosocial support. The findings therefore underscore the need for schools to look beyond visible distress and to recognize that students who consistently care for others may also require care, validation, and emotionally safe spaces for themselves.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that schools adopt a more proactive and inclusive approach to student mental health by recognizing that emotionally dependable students may also be among the most vulnerable. Guidance and psychosocial support services should expand their focus beyond students who openly manifest distress and include those who are consistently perceived as resilient, reliable, and emotionally available to others. Because the findings show that “strong friends” often remain silent due to fear of burdening others, helper identity, and high-expectation pressure, schools should not rely solely on reactive or walk-in counseling models. Instead, support systems should include intentional check-ins, psychologically safe spaces, and emotionally responsive programs that make vulnerability more acceptable for students who are used to being the source of support.

In response to this need, the study recommends the implementation of the proposed intervention program, "Support for the Supporters," as a school-based psychosocial initiative for students who frequently occupy caregiving roles within peer groups. The program may be implemented through the existing Guidance Office, homeroom periods, or student development activities, making it feasible even in resource-constrained public school settings. Its core components may include proactive identification of student peer-supporters or student leaders, supportive boundaries workshops that teach students how to care for others without neglecting themselves, care circles or safe-space sessions that promote mutual vulnerability and reciprocity, and proactive outreach by counselors or trained school personnel for students who may be unlikely to seek help independently. These components are appropriate because they directly respond to the study's findings on emotional masking, compassion fatigue, self-silencing, and unmet needs for validation, reciprocity, and safe emotional spaces.

To support effective implementation, schools may establish clear guidelines for confidentiality, emotional safety, and referral procedures. Students participating in the program should be assured that emotional disclosure will not affect their academic standing, leadership image, or peer reputation. Peer facilitators or student leaders involved in wellness activities should also be supervised by qualified school counselors or guidance personnel to prevent secondary emotional burden. In addition, psychoeducational sessions may be integrated into school wellness programs to normalize help-seeking, emotional boundary-setting, and reciprocal peer support. Over time, the program may be scaled into a broader mental health literacy initiative that benefits not only identified "strong friends" but the wider student population as well.

The findings also suggest several directions for future research. Since the present study was limited to a small group of Grade 12 students from one public senior high school, future studies may be conducted using larger samples, multiple school settings, or different educational levels to determine whether the experiences of "strong friends" are similar across contexts. Comparative studies involving public and private schools, urban and rural settings, or different cultural communities may also provide a broader understanding of how peer-support roles are shaped by context. Quantitative or mixed methods studies may further examine the prevalence of emotional burden, emotional labor, help-seeking barriers, and support gaps among adolescent peer supporters, while longitudinal studies may investigate how the strong-friend role affects well-being over time.

Further research is also recommended to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed intervention program. Future scholars may test whether programs such as Support for the Supporters improve perceived social support, emotional expression, boundary-setting, and help-seeking willingness among students who are often relied upon by peers. It may also be valuable to include the perspectives of teachers, guidance counselors, parents, and peers to better understand how the strong-friend role is reinforced, overlooked, or addressed within the school environment. Such studies would strengthen the evidence base for school-based interventions and contribute to the

development of more responsive psychosocial support systems for adolescents whose struggles are often hidden behind a façade of strength.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors affirm that this study was conducted in accordance with accepted ethical standards for research involving human participants. Prior to data collection, the participants were given a clear explanation of the purpose of the study, the nature of their participation, and the procedures involved, and informed consent was properly obtained. Participation was strictly voluntary, and each respondent was informed of the right to decline any question or withdraw from the study at any time without penalty or negative consequence. The anonymity and confidentiality of the participants were safeguarded by removing real names, sections, and other identifying details and replacing them with pseudonyms or participant codes. Data privacy was strictly observed through the secure handling of audio recordings, transcripts, and related research files, which were stored in a password-protected folder and scheduled for deletion after completion of the study. Considering the sensitive nature of the topic, the researchers also prioritized the well-being of the participants by conducting the interviews in private and psychologically safe spaces and by implementing a safety protocol, including pausing or terminating the interview when signs of distress were observed and making referral support from the School Guidance Office available when necessary. The authors further declare that no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism, fabrication, and falsification were strictly avoided, and all sources used in the manuscript were properly cited and acknowledged. The interpretation of the findings was carried out with academic honesty and fairness, and every effort was made to minimize personal bias through careful review of the narratives and faithful representation of the participants' lived experiences. The results of the study were used solely for academic and research purposes. For full disclosure, generative artificial intelligence (AI) was used only as an assistive tool for language refinement and organization of the manuscript, when applicable, and was not used to fabricate data, replace participant narratives, or substitute for the researchers' analysis, interpretation, and scholarly judgment.

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